

Discover Oncology: The Interplay Between the Food/Drug Related Nitrosogenesis Based on ROS/Nitric Oxide (NO) Interaction: The Two of the Most Powerful Factors Responsible for the Photo Nitroso Carcinogenicity Concerning the Skin Cancers Pathogenesis

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Abstract

Processes concerning concepts such as phototoxicity/ photodecomposition with subsequent development of photo carcinogenicity and skin cancer generation are also influenced/modulated by drug and food intake.

It is the drugs and foods that determine or define the concepts of Nitrosogenesis and Nitroso mediated Photo carcinogenesis of skin cancer.

Nitrosamines are well known phototoxic/ photolabile substances from the distant past, some of them also having additional carcinogenic or mutagenic effects.

The intake of nitrosamines with the drugs can be 1) in the framework of the so-called nitroso contamination or the intake of a ready carcinogen that has already occurred outside the body, such as NDEA, NMBA, NDMA, etc. or 2) they arise de novo in the organism when the following prerequisites are present: 2. 1) the presence of a secondary or tertiary amino group in the respective drugs, 2. 2) the presence of a gastric or acidic environment and 2. 3) the presence of nitrite-rich food.

In practice, it appears that diet largely defines drug-mediated mixed-type Photo Nitrosogenesis/Photo Nitroso- Carcinogenesis, and hence skin cancer incidence.

Therefore, the simultaneous intake of some nitrite-rich foods such as Broccoli, Cabbage, Carrot, Cauliflower, Celery, Cucumber, Leek, Lettuce, Parsley, Pumpkin, Red beetroot, Spinach for example, together with some drugs could appear to be risky for the skin cancer generation.

On the other hand, the food itself could also be a direct donor of finished nitrosamines such as NDMA: cured meats, fish, and alcoholic beverages like beer and whiskey/ NDEA- in processed meats.

In practice, the exogenously defined, but this time predominantly nutritionally mediated, Nitrosogenesis concerning skin cancer mirrors the drug medicated one and could also be considered as 1) exogenous, based

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on direct intake of finished carcinogens with foods, or 2) mixed type : Namely, 1) intake of nitrite-rich foods, which in 2) under stomach conditions/acidic/ and 3) intake of secondary or tertiary amines with the medication.

The greater the number of drugs taken by a patient, the higher the risk of taking 1) drugs with pure phototoxicity/not nitrosamine related/ non nitroso contamination-based effects, but also 2) those whose final photocarcinogenicity could be defined on the basis of taking 2.1) finished , completed nitrosamines, as well as 2.2) those that are subsequently converted into such.

In this context, we report a patient, who developed a high-risk tumor near the eye under systemic treatment with : (nitroso-) metoprolol, (nitroso-) torasemide, (nitroso-) rosuvastatin, (nitroso-) ezetimib, Nitroso acetylsalicylic acid (NO-ASA), (nitroso-) piroxicam , (nitroso-) dapaglifozin and (nitroso-) clopidogrel.

Whether the role of Nitrosogenesis is discussed in the context of phototoxicity or photodecomposition of nitrosamines in the human body, both processes are characterized by the subsequent generation of genotoxic/ mutagenic substances and DNA damage.

The photodecomposition of nitrosamines leads to the release of nitric oxide. The last one interacts with ROS, and this interaction could either promote or suppress carcinogenesis.

Low concentrations of NO are thought to promote carcinogenesis. The interaction between NO and ROS influences and modulates the processes directly related to carcinogenesis: angiogenesis, programmed cell death, and cell signaling.

Oxidative stress, caused by an imbalance in ROS levels, is a also key factor in the development and progression of skin cancer.

This explains why low concentrations of nitrosamines in drugs should be often considered as more dangerous than higher concentrations, as it is precisely these that promote skin cancer when interacting with ROS.

Both UVB and UVA are considered generators of ROS in the context of photo carcinogenesis. Subsequent interactions with nitric oxide reinforce the concept of photo Nitrosogenesis/carcinogenesis of skin cancer or Nitroso photo carcinogenesis/Nitroso photo genesis of skin cancer based on drug (but also food) intake.

Photocarcinogenicity related to the onset and progression of keratinocyte cancer seems to be nitroso-dependent, regardless of the mechanism by which it is generated: photodecomposition or phototoxicity: in fact the final result is the development of Nitroso Photo Carcinogenicity based on medicinal and/or dietary intake.

Correction of this type of adverse drug reactions, namely skin cancer in high-risk areas, could be successfully treated using severe reconstructive surgical techniques such as island flap.

Introduction

The pathogenesis of drug-induced photosensitivity involves both phototoxic and photoallergic mechanisms [1]. The phototoxicity of beta blockers and diuretics in general has been well-documented over the last decades [1] even before the identification and officialization of nitrosamine contamination within these two drug classes [2].

Generally, it is very important to distinguish between pure phototoxicity, cumulative phototoxicity, and the subsequent development of photocarcinogenicity on one hand, and the directly mediated carcinogenicity in rodents and bacteria via direct contact/in vitro for example [3].

Nitrosamines are not only mutagens but also substances that could contribute to probable photo toxicity/ (photodecomposition under UV light) and probable subsequent carcinogenicity, independent if the last one (NAs) posses direct carcinogenic activity or not [4].

According to recent literature data, nitroso-phototoxicity – resulting from the intake of drugs containing photocarcinogenic/ nitroso compounds like nitrosamines – has been shown to contribute to skin cancer development significantly more frequently or at

least equal than the pure photocarcinogenicity alone [5-8].

Potentially nitrosamine contaminated poly medication remains a significant concern, particularly for polymorbid patients who are chronically exposed to multiple potentially nitrosamine affected medications [5-8].

We report another case of drug-induced high-risk keratinocyte tumor – an ulcero-infiltrative basal cell carcinoma – located in the left periorbital area near the medial canthus, which developed shortly after the initiation of systemic poly medication, including potentially nitrosamine-contaminated drugs. Successful treatment was achieved through surgical excision of the lesion, followed by defect reconstruction using the island flap technique.

Case Report

A 69-year-old male presented to the dermatology department with a primary complaint of a bleeding, enlarging neoplasm beneath the left eye, present for approximately one year. Additionally, he reported a reddish lesion near the right ear that had increased in size over recent months, for which a skin biopsy was conducted.

The patient's medical history included an ischemic stroke, moderate dementia syndrome, three-vessel coronary artery disease, left ventricular dysfunction, moderate mitral regurgitation, chronic congestive heart failure, and arterial hypertension. He was on systemic medication since March 2023 with rosuvastatin/ezetimibe 20mg/10mg once daily, dapagliflozin 10 mg half a tablet in the morning, torsemide 10 mg once in the morning, metoprolol succinate 50 mg once in the morning, clopidogrel 75 mg once in the evening, acetylsalicylic acid 100 mg once in the evening, and piracetam 1200 mg twice daily. Additionally, since June 2023 citicoline 250 mg twice daily, and memantine hydrochloride 10 mg once in the morning since November 2024, were administered. Routine blood and urine tests revealed several mild abnormalities: slightly decreased MCV of 81.9 fL (normal range 82 – 96 fL), slightly decreased MCH of 26.1 pg (27-33 pg), slightly elevated PDW of 16.8% (11-15.5%), elevated RBC levels 22.0 /microL in urine (0-10 /microL), decreased HDL levels of 0.02 mmol/l (1.55-2.0 mmol/l), elevated creatinine levels of 146.5 micromol/L (61.9 – 114.9 micromol/L), elevated uric acid 486.0 micromol/L (220 – 450 micromol/L), elevated ASAT levels of 68.0 U/L (11 – 34 U/L), and elevated ALAT levels of 63.0 U/L (0 – 45 U/L).

The dermatological examination revealed a tumor-like lesion in the left periorbital area near the medial canthus, measuring approximately 1 cm. The lesion displayed an erosive surface, pearly undermined borders, and a central hemorrhagic crust. The lesion was clinically suspected for basal cell carcinoma (Fig.1). The histopathological verification of the skin biopsy of the lesion on the left auricle confirmed actinic keratosis.

Figure 1: A tumor-like lesion in the left periorbital area near the medial canthus, measuring approximately 1 cm. The lesion displays an erosive surface, pearly undermined borders, and a central hemorrhagic crust

The lesion in the left periorbital area near the medial canthus was removed with an oval excision. (Fig.2a) The primary wound defect was reconstructed with an island pedicle flap (Fig.2b). The secondary wound defect was closed with single interrupted sutures (Fig.3a,b).

Figure 2a,b: Intraoperative view: The lesion in the left periorbital area near the medial canthus is removed with an oval excision (a). The primary wound defect is then reconstructed with an island pedicle flap (b).

Figure 3a,b: Intraoperative view: Reconstruction of the primary wound defect with an island pedicle flap (a), followed by secondary defect closure with single interrupted sutures (a,b).

The histopathological evaluation revealed an extensive, well-demarcated epithelial proliferation characterized by epidermal necrosis, covered with a parakeratotic crust, proliferation of atypical basaloid keratinocytes, arranged in irregular nests and forming pseudo glandular rosettes with peripheral palisading, demarcated by a phenomenon of retraction from a lichenoid, well-vascularized, lymphoplasmacytic stroma, prominent in the mid-dermal compartment. No evidence of perineural or lympho vascular invasion was found. Resection margins were clear. The histological findings were consistent with ulceroinfiltrative basal cell carcinoma, stage I (T1bN0M0). A contrast-enhanced CT scan of the head and neck was performed without any abnormalities detected.

Discussion

The concepts of Onco-pharmacogenesis/ Pharmacocarcinogenesis and drug-induced Nitrosogenesis of skin cancer are gradually gaining recognition within the medical community, while polycontamination with nitrosamines or photocarcinogens (photolabile substances) remains a persistent and globally “unresolved” issue [5].

The periocular region remains a relatively common site for the development of high-risk basal cell carcinomas, with increasing case reports observed in association with clinicopathological correlations – specifically the link between cutaneous malignancies and potentially nitroso contaminated drug intake, including both monotherapy and poly medication [5-8]. Hou et al [9] evaluated the dose-response relationship between the use of various photosensitizing antihypertensive medications and the risk of subsequent skin cancer development.

Among 8 777 documented non-melanoma skin cancer (NMSC) cases, the use of antihypertensive drugs was

associated with significantly increased risk for NMSC: overall antihypertensives (HR [95% CI]: 1.12 [1.07-1.18]), ACE inhibitors (1.09 [1.01-1.18]), calcium channel blockers (1.13 [1.05-1.22]), diuretics (1.20 [1.12-1.27]), loop diuretics (1.17 [1.07-1.28]), and thiazides (1.17 [1.03-1.33]) [5].

The study also found a significant trend toward increased NMSC risk with the use of multiple antihypertensive agents (p -trend = 0.02) and with prolonged duration of use (p -trend < 0.01) [9]. As the authors suggested, a dose-dependent relationship was established: the greater the number and duration of antihypertensive medications taken, the higher the risk of developing skin cancers or the faster their onset [9]. The combination itself between beta blockers and loop diuretics has already been described in the literature as risky with respect to the development of multiple keratinocytic tumors and melanomas simultaneously precisely due to the possible generation of nitroso photo toxicity in the context of potential/real nitroso-contamination [7].

Similar findings have been reported for the intake of some potentially nitrosamine-contaminated antidiabetic drugs/beta blockers and the subsequent generation of keratinocytic skin tumors in areas exposed to solar radiation [5,10].

Rosuvastatin is not on the FDA list for nitroso-contaminated drugs [2], but it exists as a nitroso-contaminated product [11].

Rosuvastatin itself has been known to be phototoxic for years [12,13], but it is unclear to what extent it may also be potentiated by Nitroso -contamination as an additional bolus of phototoxicity [11].

It has a secondary amino group and could potentiate the endogenous , drug-mediated Nitrosogenesis (also

relevant to skin cancer) in the presence of an acidic environment and nitrite-rich food.

Dapagliflozin is not represented on the FDA list for nitroso-contaminated products [2], nor is it currently associated with the generation of phototoxicity within monomedication.

Does not contain secondary and tertiary amines. The drug may be contaminated with nitrosamines within the drug manufacturing process/ or in the context of so-called exogenous, drug-mediated Nitrosogenesis.

Clopidogrel exists as nitroso- contamination [14], but definitive data on the phototoxicity of the preparation are currently lacking. Rather, data are available on Clopidogrel intake and the development of photosensitivity [15].

It contains a tertiary amino group which, in the presence of nitrite and an acidic environment, could favour the generation of nitrosamines, which are also known as photocarcinogens. It could be considered as a potential participant in the processes of drug related Nitrosogenesis.

Piracetam also exists as nitroso contamination [16]. Piracetam is characterized as a secondary amine due to the presence of a nitrogen atom bonded to two carbon atoms within its molecular structure.

In practice and under certain conditions, it could potentiate the formation of nitrosamines in the stomach. Involved in endogenous, drug mediated Nitrosogenesis.

Acetyl salicylic acid has been well known for its phototoxicity action for years [17].

Contains no secondary or tertiary amino group.

Nitrosamine contamination in acetylsalicylic acid (aspirin) can occur when secondary or tertiary amines react with nitrous acid, which can be formed from nitrites under acidic conditions [18]. These nitrosamines are potential carcinogens, and regulatory authorities have established guidelines for acceptable levels in pharmaceuticals [19].

Some studies have shown that when ASA is administered in the form of a nitric oxide-donating aspirin (NO-ASA), it can lead to increased plasma nitrate levels.

These elevated nitrate levels can be converted to nitrite in the body, particularly in the oral cavity and stomach. If these nitrites then react with amines (which may be present in food or drug formulations), they can form nitrosamines.

This potential for nitrosamine formation is a concern, particularly in the context of long-term use of NO-ASA.

Ezetimibe exists in the form of nitroso contamination or N nitroso impurity 4 [20], while it is currently not associated officially with the generation of phototoxicity.

Ezetimibe contains a tertiary amino group and under certain conditions should be able to potentiate the

formation of nitrosamines and hence phototoxicity within endogenously related Nitrosogenesis.

Data on possible nitroso contamination and phototoxicity are lacking for citicoline and memantine hydrochloride.

Some beta-blockers have been associated with photoinduced cutaneous reactions [21,22].

Unfortunately, epidemiological studies have not evaluated the association between individual beta-blockers use and the skin cancer risk.

Rather, the evidence has been presented with all beta-blockers grouped into a single category of exposure [23].

A meta-analysis based on one case-control and two cohort studies found that beta-blocker use was associated with modestly increased risk of BCC (OR 1.09, 95% CI 1.04–1.15) compared to non-use, but was not associated with the incidence of SCC (OR 0.89, 95% CI 0.69–1.16) [24].

Another meta-analysis, which included two cohort studies, reported no association with risk of keratinocyte cancer [23].

Based on these data, it could be reasonably assumed that the photosensitivity/phototoxicity of beta blockers is not structurally determined as it is not constant. It seems to be not constant in terms of reproduction in the context of drug intake, but also in terms of type of response: phototoxicity or photosensitivity [1,24].

This fact leads clinicians to seriously consider whether the cause of so-called drug related phototoxicity has fundamentally different roots than the structurally one. On the other hand, there is evidence that drugs that are fundamentally different in their structure lead to so-called "irregularly reproducing phototoxicity" or photo decomposition [1].

This phototoxicity/ photodecomposition, instability under UV light/ also appears to be a structurally determinant or serious basis with regard to skin cancer development and progression [1].

A recently identified contaminant in medications, also known as nitrosamines, turns out to be not only genotoxic, carcinogenic or mutagenic substances but also notorious photocarcinogens [2].

Many beta blockers contain a secondary, but also a tertiary amino group. Under gastric conditions and in the presence of nitrite rich food, this favours the formation of nitrosamines in the context of so-called endogenous drug-mediated Nitrosogenesis/ mixed type Nitrosogenesis (FOOD / DRUG RELATED NITROSOGENESIS of skin cancer).

Based on the anamnestic data of our patients one could come to the following conclusions or logical assumptions:

1) The polydrug intake in the described patient includes the known phototoxic drugs according to the scientific literature already available to date, such as

rosuvastatin, acetyl salicylic acid, metoprolol and torsemide.

2) Nitroso contamination/ - or the formation of Nitroso compounds in the body has been described as possible with each of the three drugs.

3) Some of the drugs mentioned are included in the FDA list as contaminated preparations containing nitrosamines which also have a definite "potential" carcinogenic effect, such as metoprolol and torsemide, for example.

4) Other preparations are not included in the list of FDAs for potential carcinogenicity but have been withdrawn from the market due to established nitroso contamination or endogenous formation of nitrosamines in the body: acetyl salicylic acid [26] and rosuvastatin for example.

Acetyl salicylic acid is risky in terms of its contamination with nitrosamines and their derivatives within the manufacturing process.

In contrast, however, Rosuvastatin possesses a tertiary amino group and thus favors in gastric conditions and in the presence of nitrites, should potentiate the formation of active nitrosamines/carcinogens or photocarcinogens.

5) Torasemide also contains a tertiary amino group, analogous to rosuvastatin.

6) Endogenous Nitrosogenesis is of concern with acetylsalicylic acid, rosuvastatin and torsemide. It should not be overlooked that several drugs undergo nitrosation in the stomach/ or so-called endogenous Nitrosogenesis (MIXED TYPE/ FOOD/DRUG RELATED NITROSOGENESIS) and only then become active carcinogenic substances, namely when they enter an acidic environment.

The processes of phototoxicity/ photodecomposition of the nitrosamines with the subsequent development of photo carcinogenicity seems to be responsible for skin cancer development and progression. Many of these processes are complex and start in the gastrointestinal tract.

All of these should be the basis of regulatory and prevention programs.

The nitroso-defined phototoxicity/ photo decomposition of a drug should be distinguished from so-called structurally determined or "otherwise mediated phototoxicity".

It appears quite possible that both problematic issues are complementary: nitroso-mediated phototoxicity/ or photodecomposition and another type of probably structurally conditioned phototoxicity/ photocarcinogenicity.

Their differentiation could be made possible and facilitated by formalization of the respective nitrosamines or nitroso derivatives in medicinal preparations.

Due to the possibility of nitrosamines forming in the stomach and in the presence of nitrites as an additional dietary/pathogenetic factor, it would be probably appropriate to indicate on the packaging of medicines whether the medicine in question contains secondary or tertiary amines and to perceive these as an additional risk factor for the patients. These medicines should not be taken with nitrite-rich foods.

The risk potential of 1) concomitant intake of a medication containing secondary or tertiary amines with 2) nitrite-rich foods in 3) an acidic or gastric environment should also be particularly emphasized.

Not without significance is the fact or dilemma for patients: which foods could contain 1) pure photo carcinogens or 2) high nitrite content and form active photocarcinogens, also known as nitrosamines, when certain medications are taken, namely: cured and processed meats, such as bacon, ham, hot dogs, and deli meats.

And there are also some vegetables that naturally contain nitrates and nitrites and could be also problematic in relation to the FOOD/DRUG mediated Nitrosogenesis concerning the skin cancer development and progression. These include Broccoli, Cabbage, Carrot, Cauliflower, Celery, Cucumber, Endive, Fennel, Leek, Lettuce, Parsley, Pumpkin, Red beetroot, Spinach.

Another controversial issue in the context of drug-mediated Nitrosogenesis or carcinogenesis remains the following: is there a difference between the concepts of photodecomposition and phototoxicity mediated by nitrosamines? Is this important?

Phototoxicity and photodecomposition are distinct phenomena involving light and chemical reactions, but they differ in their effects.

Phototoxicity is a toxic reaction in living tissue triggered by light [27], while photodecomposition is the breakdown of a substance into simpler components due to light exposure [28].

Photo dissociation, photolysis, photodecomposition, or photo fragmentation is a chemical reaction in which molecules of a chemical compound are broken down by absorption of light (photons). It is defined as the interaction of one or more photons with one target molecule that dissociates into two fragments [28].

Cumulative mediated phototoxicity based on the intake of phototoxic medications also increases the risk of developing skin cancer, i.e., DNA damage and tumor cell generation [23].

Nitrosamines, often found as byproducts in CO₂ capture processes, can be decomposed by photodecomposition, specifically UV irradiation [29,30].

This process breaks the N-N bond in nitrosamines, forming products like nitric oxide radical and other potentially less harmful compounds [29,30].

Nitric oxide (NO), a free radical, plays a complex and sometimes contradictory role in cancer [31]. It can act as both a pro-tumor and anti-tumor agent depending on its concentration and the specific cancer type [31,32].

At low concentrations, NO can promote tumor growth by stimulating angiogenesis (new blood vessel formation) and cell proliferation [31]. However, at higher concentrations, NO can exhibit cytotoxic and cytostatic effects, leading to cancer cell death and inhibiting tumor growth [31,32]. Nitric oxide could be also genotoxic and also proangiogenic agent [31].

The specifics of the manufacturing process of a drug, the chemical structure of the product itself (presence of secondary/tertiary amino groups), and the dietary habits of the patients - these are what underlie the concept of the so called MIXED TYPE, FOOD-DRUG TYPE related Nitrosogenesis/ Photo Nitroso Carcinogenesis and purely exogenous drug or FOOD type related Nitrosogenesis, and hence the generation and incidence of skin cancer. It seems that exactly these differences account for the divergent or percentage varying results of the heterogeneous follow-ups on the subject worldwide.

Additional consideration should be given to pure photocarcinogenicity based on drug intake, but in the absence of any nitroso component.

It is precisely the photodecomposition of nitrosamines and the release of NO/nitric oxide, as well as the subsequent interaction with ROS, that are key elements in the cascade that regulate skin cancer [33].

The release of nitric oxide in the skin after exposure to solar radiation is not new and may have not only beneficial effects, as described in the literature [34].

Ultraviolet light mediates the release of a powerful pro carcinogenic mediator (nitric oxide/NO) through photolysis/photodegradation [35], which subsequently proves to be key to the generation of skin cancer.

Low concentrations of NO/nitric oxide (which are often found in medicines or food, for example) and high concentrations of ROS, according to international literature data, could define carcinogenesis related to cutaneous melanoma, breast cancer, and colon cancer [36].

ROS plays a key role in the development of skin cancer: its overproduction is associated with a genotoxic/mutagenic effect on skin cells (36). Together with NO/nitric oxide, they have a pro tumorigenic, synergistic effect on skin cancer in general, which is concentration dependent [37].

This is precisely how, in patients with BCC, for example, a combination of low NO and high ROS levels may create an environment that favors uncontrolled keratinocyte proliferation.

NO can initiate melanoma progression through a feedback loop apurinic / apyrimidinic endonuclease -1/ redox factor 1 (APE /Ref-1) [38].

Low concentrations of NO/nitric oxide potentiate keratinocyte proliferation and are potential inducers of tumor growth [39].

Solar radiation is the most serious generator of ROS and, therefore, a possible inducer of processes such as DNA fragmentation [40].

Nitrosamines, when exposed to UV light, can release nitric oxide (NO) [41].

Nitrosamines in medicines (but also those in food) could also prove to be an endless, permanent generator of NO/nitric oxide for the human body [42], especially after exposure to solar radiation and the subsequent photodecomposition of the aforementioned.

Exposure to solar radiation and the generation of ROS further contribute to the generation and progression of skin cancer because of the induction of DNA mutations [43].

Regulators such as the FDA/EMA do not consider the repeatedly proven (scientific) carcinogenic effect (in relation to skin cancer, but not only) of these metabolites (NO/ROS), which makes carcinogenicity tests (CPCA/Ames tests) almost completely clinically inapplicable or practically unusable.

The clinical-pathological correlations in the intake of (even low doses) of nitrosamine-contaminated medicinal products/nitric oxide generators after exposure to solar radiation, as well as 2) the subsequent development of skin cancer in real patients from another [5-8,10], are clearly indicative of the potential/actual carcinogenic effect of nitric oxide and ROS, similar to the international scientific experimental data shared so far.

The pure carcinogenic effect of unmetabolized nitrosamine (NDEA, NDMA, etc.) remains unclear, as does the mutagenic effect of the mutagenic or carcinogenic metabolites produced after its metabolism. These could contribute significantly to the additional pure carcinogenic effect that has been associated for years with various forms of cancer in the human body. There is a lack of data on this topic in scientific literature.

Nitrosamines in medicinal products, in the context of their photodecomposition, could be the source of one of the most serious pro carcinogenic mediators – Nitric oxide, which is involved in the genesis of skin cancer.

Much to the regret of end users, this is most likely the reason why regulators do not officially acknowledge the presence of nitrosamines/generators for nitric oxide in drugs: this would be equivalent to establishing/formalizing, metaphorically speaking, a "chronicle of a death predicted in advance"—not only for patients, but also for regulators and pharmaceutical companies.

Regarding defect closure, reconstructive techniques are particularly valuable when managing defects in anatomically challenging areas, especially within the facial region [44,45].

Restoration of a primary defect near the medial canthus can be complex, and achieving aesthetically satisfactory postoperative results is always preferable [46].

In this case, the use of an island flap allowed for effective reconstruction while avoiding the need for second intervention or a more invasive surgical approach.

Island flap seems to be a good option for keratinocyte medial cathus located BCC [47,48].

Conclusions

Based on the available scientific literature, it could be concluded that the data link nitrosamines either to phototoxicity [4] or to photodecomposition [28,29]. Both subsequently activated mechanisms are associated with a pro carcinogenic / genotoxic effect, which most likely corresponds pathogenetically/clinically to the onset of skin cancer [5-8].

The ongoing “saga” of nitrosamine-related events - ranging from contamination to Nitroso Photo toxicity and Nitroso Photo carcinogenicity - raises critical questions about whether these mechanisms have been fully understood.

Variability in the concentrations and numbers of present nitrosamines found in medications and food may contribute to the occurrence of multiple or rapidly progressing skin cancers.

Emerging evidence indicates that these mechanisms of phototoxicity / photo decomposition are closely connected to photo nitroso carcinogenicity, and the underlying pathways are gradually being unraveled.

The concept of DRUG but also FOOD mediated Nitrosogenesis is becoming increasingly plausible, as both large-scale studies and smaller case reports have established clinicopathological correlations between nitrosamine exposure and subsequent skin cancer development and progression. Given these findings, it appears that “The Era of Drug related Nitrosogenesis” is not only possible - but already unfolding.

The data [49] confirming the clinico-pathological correlations shared in this publication [3,5-8,10] remain encouraging, namely due to the fact that: 1) the Photo genotoxicity/Photo Nitroso carcinogenicity of certain nitrosamines (such as nitrosoproline, for example), after exposure to ultraviolet radiation and without metabolic activation, on human-derived keratinocytes, is an indisputable fact [49]. Similar data are available for nitrosomorpholine [50], recently discovered in medicines as a nitroso contaminant [51].

The phototoxicity/photocarcinogenicity of certain nitrosamines after exposure to ultraviolet radiation could be mediated in the form of two different

mechanisms: 1) micronuclei formation in keratinocytes on the one hand, and direct release of pro carcinogenic nitric oxide (NO) on the other [49]. The experimental model described [49] is reciprocal and fully consistent with the clinical pathological correlations recently published in the scientific literature.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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